

THE INFLUENCE OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON ROMANIAN ENTREPRENEURSHIP FROM THE PERSPECTIVES OF INNOVATION AND RISK-TAKING

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Abstract

Purpose – *This study endeavors to determine how Romanian SMEs have weathered the disruptions created by the COVID-19 pandemic taking into account the lockdown implemented as a consequence of the declared state of emergency.*

Methodology/approach – *We have considered it beneficial to observe both the capacity for innovation in the face of new challenges, and also the degree of risk-taking during a period marked by uncertainty. The survey method was used, with the questionnaire as a research tool.*

Findings – *The effects of the pandemic have negatively impacted 80% of the companies participating in this study. SMEs in Romania have a reduced capacity to take risks and to innovate in the post-state of emergency context.*

Research limitations/implications – *The study was conducted immediately after the end of the state of emergency, but the effects on companies may appear in the longer term.*

Practical implications – *The study was conducted in the period after the suspension of emergency measures imposed by the state of emergency, when effects and solutions presented themselves more closer to the state of emergency.*

Originality/value – *We connected the parameters of innovation and risk-taking with the effects generated by the imposition of the state of emergency.*

Key words: *entrepreneurial orientation, state of emergency, SMEs*

Introduction

The pandemic debuted in Romania at the beginning of 2020 after other European states had already been affected by the COVID-19 virus. Similarly to other countries impacted by it, Romania implemented several restrictive measures regarding both the isolation and distancing of individuals, and its economic activities. On March 16th 2020 a national state of emergency was declared that lasted until May 15th 2020.

The measures imposed by the government resulted in major changes from a cultural standpoint as well as in the way people interacted. Under such conditions, entrepreneurs as agents of opportunity and disruption have immediately felt the impact of these changes. Therefore, enterprises headed by entrepreneurs, depending on their methods of engagement and various intervening factors, may or may not have endured on the market, they have either prospered or experienced failures. In Romania, based on the research conducted, SMEs seem to have been considerably more affected by the COVID-19 pandemic than their larger enterprise counterparts. In this context, the current study intends to uncover the state of SMEs after the implementation of the COVID-19 emergency measures starting with an analysis of the specialized literature regarding the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on SMEs, and also through a descriptive method of research using quantitative data based on a questionnaire geared towards entrepreneurs from different locations in Romania.

In order to assess the way in which SMEs have weathered the crisis generated by the COVID-19 pandemic, we have deemed it relevant to look at their entrepreneurial orientation, since it is the

prerequisite strategy in the face this type of crisis and of the consequent changes in the business landscape (Vanessa Ratten, 2020).

Entrepreneurial orientation “encompasses firm-level behavioral characteristics of engaging in product-market innovation, promoting innovative behavior within the firm, undertaking somewhat risky ventures, and being the first to come up with proactive innovations” (Wang and Altinay, 2012). Therefore, the main elements necessary for tackling the COVID-19 crisis include innovation and risk-taking.

The pandemic changed the way in which economic activity is carried out, and a return to a pre-pandemic normal cannot be anticipated, as to this very moment the fight against the virus and its variants continues.

As such, it is of interest to identify existing opportunities and innovative solutions to be able to meet the new challenges generated by the COVID-19 pandemic. To this end, innovative thinking and a high degree of risk-taking are necessary.

A possible first step could be outlining SMEs from the perspective of their capacity for innovation and risk assumption, followed by innovation stimulation and risk assumption in areas where it proves necessary, and by their continuous search for new methods of innovation in the given context.

Literature Review

After more than a year and a half since the first reported COVID-19 case in Romania (February 26th) the consequences the business environment had to face are stark in light of the exceptional measures implemented meant to limit the spread of the virus. For the purpose of identifying these consequences, research studies have been conducted even prior to the first pandemic year’s end. One of these early studies was published by MKOR Consulting in 2020, titled “Impact of the COVID-19 Epidemic on the Romanian Business Environment”. According to this study, even at that point in time 91% of companies reported being affected by the Coronavirus epidemic, and 95% had taken some measures to endure in the face of the crisis brought on by COVID-19, the most frequent of which were financial measures, followed by measures of employee protection, and pivoting business activities. The study highlights the fact that resilience in the face of this crisis depends on the size of the organization, therefore, the larger the company the better chance it has at survival, as per figure 1 Crisis resilience based on the size of the organization.

Source: MKOR Study: *Impact of the COVID-19 Epidemic on the Romanian Business Environment*

Figure 1 Crisis resilience based on the size of the organization

Additionally, the impact affecting small businesses is much more significant compared to the one their larger counterparts experienced. The resulting impact decreases in intensity depending on the size of the type of organization as seen in Figure 2 Impact based on organization type.

Source: MKOR Study: *Impact of the COVID-19 Epidemic on the Romanian Business Environment*

Figure 2. Impact based on organization type

As a result of the research analysis carried out by MKOR, representatives of the business environment showcased limited trust in government institutions regarding the management of the COVID-19 crisis. The average trust level settling at 2.7 points of a total of 7. Many studies confirm the fact that multiple SMEs have been affected by the new environment brought on by the pandemic (Antonescu, D. 2020). The effects generated by COVID-19 in the SME sector have also been detected at the level of entrepreneurial initiatives, as irrespective of their legal status in March 2019, a 74% decrease was recorded the following year compared to 2019 (Antonescu, D. 2020 pag.19).

Unexpectedly, in March 2020 the number of company dissolutions and suspensions of activity decreased compared to March 2019. Despite its negative outcomes, opportunities generated by the COVID-19 crisis have also been identified. Some of these are the disruption of import supply chain which can lead to an increase sale of local products (Antonescu, D. 2020 pag.24), the increase of public investment in education, agriculture and the food industry, the stimulation of local consumption, the issuance of food vouchers to the unemployed, supporting large enterprises, promoting innovation for purchases and identifying innovative solutions in the fight against COVID-19.

Another noted opportunity lies within the IT sector for which this period has created the necessary contextual momentum to transition into its next level of development, of creating new products and services. Additionally, the telecommunications industry could also signal an opportunity since the need for a fast internet connection is larger than ever.

Furthermore, the National Institute of Statistics (NIS) put forth an experimental research paper titled *Experimental research: Assessment of the COVID - 19 impact on the economic environment in March and April 2020*. A relevant aspect is the timing of the research, the questionnaire was addressed to economic agents on the 17th to the 19th of March 2020 before other COVID-19 preventive measures were implemented.

The NIS study reveals a high degree of uncertainty regarding the future of business spanning March and April 2020, and an increase in uncertainty in April 2020 compared to March of the same year.

In 2021 a somewhat optimistic outlook returned among business leaders to the point where half of them anticipated a return to normal economic activity, as per the 2021 edition of the KPMG CEO Outlook Pulse.

According to the EY attractiveness study, in 2021 Romania benefited from an above average attractiveness compared to the European investor average, with 66% of investors planning to establish or expand their operations in Romania in the following 12 month, compared to only 27% in 2020.

Another research report regarding the COVID-19 pandemic's impact on Romanian companies was conducted by BDO Romania, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University Iasi and the Iasi Chamber of Commerce and Industry with the objective of evaluating the evolution of Romanian companies during the first year

of the COVID-19 pandemic (February 2020 – February 2021), and showcasing their outlook for that year.

The most highlighted success factors during the pandemic were teleworking, enactment of public health protection measures, and limiting investment and the quality of managerial decision-making.

In terms of opportunities, 28.7% of our respondents did not identify opportunities, while 11.9% did not need to search. Even so, based on the remaining answers, opportunities in the online environment, the emergence of new markets, as well as products for special needs have been noted.

Digitization and process improvement were identified as the strongest outcomes of the year 2021.

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

In this study the model of entrepreneurial orientation has served as a lens for the purpose of examining the association between innovation, risk-taking and the ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The model of entrepreneurial orientation comprises the methods, practices and styles of the decision-making process that entrepreneurs use in order to act entrepreneurially. In 1983 entrepreneurial orientation was defined by Miller as “an entrepreneurial firm is one that engages in product-market innovation, undertakes somewhat risky ventures, and is first to come up with ‘proactive’ innovations, beating competitors to the punch”. Based on this we can deduce the existence of three dimensions for testing entrepreneurship: innovation, pro-activeness and risk-taking.

The current study has taken on the two dimensions of entrepreneurial orientation, innovation and risk-taking starting from the fact that the COVID-19 pandemic is one of the most devastating crises of modern times, and as such, during turbulent times when organizations have to bear unforeseen changes, creativity is of crucial importance. Researchers have recognized creativity as a method of dealing with uncertainty by testing old hypotheses and trying out new ones (Ford, 1996). Therefore, creativity in turn requires the ability to innovate and try, and to take on risks.

As supported by recent studies of the COVID-19 crisis, innovation is crucial for companies not only to be able to endure, but also to be able to prosper in the post-COVID-19 world (Chesbrough, 2020; Cohen and Cromwell, 2020).

Innovativeness suggests a company's tendency to commit to and support new ideas, while risk-taking implies taking on large debts or making significant commitments in terms of resources by capitalizing on market opportunities. Innovation can be interpreted as being a creative thinking model that generates ideas for a company.

The resilience of small and medium-sized enterprises during crises has become a subject of research since the last global financial crisis of 2007-2008. Recent studies note that SMEs are heterogeneous and the way they approach the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic differs (Lim et al., 2020). Thus, some studies note that small businesses are not directly affected by the negative effects of an economic crisis (Davidsson & Gordon, 2016) as a result of their high ability to identify opportunities (Beliaeva et al., 2020; Devece et al., 2016). Certain studies note that SMEs have the strength to overcome the COVID-19 crisis when they engage in organization-wide innovation (Morgan et al., 2020).

Therefore, according to various studies the existence of a financial crisis can represent an opening for opportunity for some SMEs, while for others it can be a threat, and in the current landscape the ability to innovate plays an important part.

The COVID-19 crisis is marked by uncertainty, since, unlike other crises, it is new and extends over an unpredictable period of time, significantly hindering future planning.

An entrepreneurial approach, an inclination towards innovation and risk-taking is required in order to deal with COVID-19. Institutional collaboration is also necessary to assist companies in such unprecedented situations

Research hypotheses of the present study are as follows:

1. The ability to withstand the COVID-19 crisis is significantly influenced by innovation

2. The ability to withstand the COVID-19 crisis is significantly influenced by risk-taking
3. Most companies have been impacted by the effects of COVID-19
4. Companies with a higher number of employees experienced a smaller impact on their business brought on by the preventive measures of COVID-19
5. Companies that introduced new concepts/services/products experienced a smaller decline in income compared to others that did not
6. Most companies found remaining in the market following the situation generated by COVID-19 to be more risky than entering the market
7. The activity of most companies underwent significant changes following the implementation of the state of emergency measures
8. Companies that benefited from government support anticipate a faster return to normal than those that did not

Methodology

The survey method was used, with the questionnaire as a research tool.

Sample and procedure

The participants of this study are Romanian entrepreneurs. The questionnaire was disseminated online on social platforms (LinkedIn and Facebook). The confidentiality and anonymity of the participants is guaranteed. The questions are close ended. The profile of respondents was selected according to their gender, age and the size of the company based on number of employees.

Findings

The effects of the pandemic have negatively impacted 80 percent of the companies participating in this study. The most affected areas of activity have been services – 45.5 percent and manufacturing – 36.6 percent. Among the most negative consequences are a decrease in turnover – 30 percent, unemployment – 20 percent, contract termination, cash flow problems, and suspension of activity – 14.9 percent each, respectively. The measures adopted to counter the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic include deferred payments, temporary paid leave, drafting programs and investment projects in order to obtain non-reimbursable funds, cost reduction, finding new buyers, and cost reduction for services. 95 percent of companies have taken measures to be able to withstand the current crisis. Companies that experienced a decline on March 1st 2020 compared to March 1st of 2019 estimated a continued decline for this year as well.

Conclusion and Future Directions

The effects of the COVID-19 pandemic have been felt globally due to the interconnectedness of economies worldwide, and Romania is no exception. All countries have intervened to mitigate losses in their respective national economies by adopting a series of fiscal measures aiming to diminish the effects of the crisis generated by the pandemic. But the measures that have been adopted to prevent the spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, such as social distancing, have led to the total or partial suspension of business activities of many companies around the world. Companies are facing financial adversity that is difficult to manage in this context, and with the surge of inflation a medium-term effect will be the increase of interest rates on deposits and loans.

After two years characterized by hesitancy due to the COVID-19 pandemic, 2022 is set to be a difficult year with many uncertainties, both at the business level and at the geopolitical level. The increase in interest rates in the context of rising inflation will mark a year in decline, our saving and investment behaviors will change. The impact of this crisis will not only be felt at the economic level, it will also influence all aspects of everyday life.

A first step towards recovery could be to direct economic activity towards sustainable development. The context of the COVID-19 epidemic, the war that is in full swing, and the recession that has spread worldwide could prove to be a significant moment for Romanian companies should they choose to seize the opportunity. They could gauge the gaps in the atypical challenges of the present context, and could strategically adapt and start developing sustainably, creating value for all stakeholders.

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APPENDIX

QUESTIONNAIRE

1. What is the current status of your business?
 - Active
 - Inactive
2. What is your number of employees?
 - Up to 10 employees
 - Between 11-50 employees
 - 50-250 employees
3. Has the number of employees changed because of the situation created by COVID-19?
 - NO
 - YES, the number has decreased
 - NO, the number has increased
4. How did you carry out your activities during the state of emergency (the first half 2020)?
 - Offline
 - Online
 - Both online and offline
5. Point out the degree of impact that COVID-19 and the implemented preventive measures have had on your business
 - Great impact
 - Medium impact
 - Small impact
 - No impact
 - It's too early for an evaluation
 - Other
6. In what way have COVID-19 and the implemented preventive measures affected revenue in the first half of 2020?
 - Revenue decrease up to 3%
 - Revenue decrease between 30-50%
 - Revenue decrease over 50%
 - Revenue increased
 - It's too early for an evaluation
 - Other
7. Have you accessed loans to deal with issues caused by COVID-19?
 - YES
 - NO
8. Have you adjusted your performance goals as a result of the situation created by COVID-19?
 - Yes, significantly reduced
 - Yes, moderately reduced
 - Maintained goals
 - Significantly increased
 - It's too early for such a decision
14. Has your company benefited from governmental support in order to overcome this situation?
 - YES
 - NO
15. Specify how your business has been affected by COVID-19 until now?
 - Decrease in demand for products/services
 - Increase in demand for products/services
 - Inability to meet contractual terms due to disruptions in logistics
 - Increase in human resource costs
 - Uncertainty and inability to make business decisions
 - Investments
 - Financial difficulties
 - Understaffing
 - Layoffs
 - Other
16. What company-wide measures have you implemented to prevent the spread of COVID-19?
 - Teleworking
 - Reduced working time
 - Reduced production / reduced commercial operations
 - Temporary reduction in production/interruption of commercial operations
 - International travel restriction
 - National travel restriction
 - Reduction / restriction of face to face meetings (events, conferences, meetings)
 - Diminished schedule
 - Sanitization of common areas
 - Providing hand sanitizers for employees working in the office
 - The use of masks and gloves
 - Other
17. If COVID-19 were to disappear, how long do you think it would take for your company to return to normal?
 - Less than 1 month
 - 1-3 months
 - 3-6 months
 - 6-9 months
 - 9-12 months

- More than 12 months
 - It's too early to predict
18. Is your business unable to cope, will you have to suspend activities?
- YES
 - NO
 - It's too early
19. Have you implemented new concepts to deal with COVID-19?
- YES
 - NO
20. Did you develop new services or products in 2020?
- YES
 - NO
21. Have you adopted a new business strategy to meet the challenges caused by COVID-19?
- YES
 - NO
22. Do your employees have the opportunity to implement new ideas within the company?
- YES
 - NO
23. Do you often adapt your products/services based on customer requirements/reviews?
- Often
 - Sometimes
 - Rarely
24. Have you changed your portfolio of services/products according to the new demands generated by the COVID-19 situation?
- YES
 - NO
24. Have you benefited from business development and innovation consulting?
- YES
 - NO
25. From your point of view which situation was more risky?
- Entering the market
 - Remaining on the market in the context of the COVID-19 situation
26. Do you use documents and established procedures to implement risk analysis?
- YES
 - NO
27. Specify your main area of activity:
- Agriculture, animal farming, fishing, hunting, forestry
 - Mining industry
 - The processing industry
 - Utilities sector (electricity, gas, water)
 - Construction
 - Wholesale and retail
 - Transportation and distribution
 - Hospitality and catering
 - Finance and insurance
 - Real estate
 - Education
 - Health and social care
 - Other
28. Specify your gender
- Female
 - Male
29. What is your age group?
- 18-25
 - 25-40
 - 40-60
 - over 60
30. When did you start your business?
- Before 2000
 - 2000-2019
 - 2020-2021